

Understanding Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) and Mental Health Disparities in Bangladeshi Women: A Mixed Method Approach

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Abstract

Background: PCOS is a common hormonal disorder that affects women's well-being. It is a chronic ailment without a cure, and poses a significant threat to women's health, with many going women untreated.

Aims: Many women in Bangladesh lack knowledge about PCOS, leading to delays in diagnosis and treatment. This gap hinders the understanding of coping strategies, treatment options, and lifestyle improvements related to this condition.

Methods: In total, 426 participants were included in this mixed methods study, and data were collected via a mixed-methods approach. A standard approach was used for the assessment of among Bangladeshi people's knowledge about PCOS signs, and symptoms, causes, diagnosis, and treatment options, and impacts on health. The prevalence of diagnostic tests among people and the extent to which women are underdiagnosed were also determined.

Results: A positive PCOS status had a significantly negative impact on mental health conditions. The knowledge levels about PCOS among participants were low (63.7%), moderate (21.6%), or high (14.7%). We found significant associations between knowledge level and age, education, occupation, place of residence, screening practices, and PCOS status (p -value <0.05). Notably, 63.4% of women in Bangladesh remain undiagnosed and have a symptomatic appearance.

Conclusion: A significant number of women have limited knowledge about PCOS. Moreover, these studies failed to assess PCOS status, even though the prevalence of PCOS is more than thirty percent. Hence, it is important to arrange a health education initiative aimed at educating and encouraging women to actively engage in the diagnostic process to prevent PCOS complications.

Introduction

PCOS is a prevalent hormonal illness that affects women's physical and psychological health. It is a chronic condition that cannot be cured with medicine. Several symptoms associated with PCOS include

irregular periods, hirsutism, high testosterone levels, metabolic disorders, ovarian cysts, excessive hair loss, insulin resistance, acne, etc. An irregular period is the major sign of PCOS and hormonal imbalance. Irregular periods or menstrual abnormalities are the first and

More Information

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foremost symptoms that are commonly observed in PCOS patients and symptomatic PCOS patients. According to Abu-Taha et al. (2020), 90.3% of women knew that irregular periods or no menstrual cycle were signs of PCOS [1]. PCOS is a major cause of infertility in women. PCOS can cause significant psychological conditions, such as reactive depression, anxiety, and hypertension.

PCOS has become an existential danger to women, with an estimated 8–13% of women worldwide of reproductive age having the disorder and 70% not receiving treatment. Studies from the United Arab Emirates, Thailand, and South India reported a prevalence of PCOS as high as 50.1% [2]. The condition has spread like a wildfire. This is the reason we concentrated on PCOS rather than other illnesses, as it currently most significantly affects the health of women. Approximately, 5–15% of females under the age of 18–44 worldwide suffer from this prevalent endocrine circumstance [3]. The black paw of women with PCOS typically strikes women with a family history of obesity, type 2 diabetes, or infertility. Depression, psychological disorders, and type 2 diabetes are more common in women with PCOS [4]. Currently, this disease is very common in women, triggering them to live an abnormal life and eventually develop endometrial cancer, cardiovascular diseases, or infertility. Approximately 40% of teenage girls with irregular periods have ultrasound-confirmed polycystic ovaries [5]. A PCOS patient may have severe trauma and reactive depression. Her self-confidence is undermined by a masculine body image that typically consists of excess weight in the upper body and hirsutism or unsightly facial hair. According to Fauser et al. (2012), 70% of women with PCOS exhibit hirsutism [5].

In addition to experiencing rapid weight gain, dietary limitations and difficulties in losing weight might contribute to a woman's depression. Over half of people with PCOS are often obese, which is a significant side effect of the disease [6]. Approximately 44% of women with PCOS are obese overall [7]. Psychological and behavioral problems, such as eating and sexual disorders, dysfunctional relationships, and a lower quality of life, are more prevalent among PCOS patients [5]. Numerous studies have demonstrated that reactive depression and mild psychological disorders are common in hirsute PCOS patients [8]. Patients with PCOS frequently endure infertility. Cardiovascular issues, neurological and psychological consequences on quality of life (such as depression and anxiety), and endometrial and breast cancers are all linked to PCOS. Polycystic ovarian syndrome, or PCOS, is frequently referred to as the most prevalent cause of anovulatory infertility in women [9]. Generally, PCOS patients are very sensitive to dietary imbalances and irregular

lifestyles. PCOS risk factors include an improper diet, lifestyle, and any infectious medicine [3]. They have to strictly maintain healthy food and a routine lifestyle. They are strictly restricted from having junk and packaged foods, sea foods, and allergenic foods. In addition, the course of therapy is very expensive. Thus, the majority of women never receive a diagnosis. Additionally, there is no specific drug that may be used to cure PCOS. PCOS can be managed with a change in lifestyle, including consuming nutritious foods, exercising, engaging in more physical activity, maintaining a positive atmosphere, etc. However, lifestyle changes are an established reason for various noncommunicable diseases [10].

However, in the least developed nations, such as Bangladesh, this maintenance is extremely difficult. Poverty can exacerbate health inequalities, impacting women's ability to afford essential healthcare services and medications. It can also make it difficult to navigate the healthcare system or advocate for themselves. All of these factors negatively affect the mental health of PCOS sufferers as do those who only experience symptoms, but do not receive a diagnosis. According to one study, PCOS is becoming more common; however, although many students have symptoms of this disease, few of them are aware of it [11]. Eighty-four percent of women had no prior knowledge of PCOS, according to Wasata et al. [12]. The lack of knowledge among Bangladeshi women regarding PCOS, its signs, and its impact on mental health may cause a delay in diagnosis and treatment. Only 38% of women are aware that mental health diseases, which include depression and anxiety, exist, according to research on the assessment of awareness of mental health conditions [13]. Overall, this problem has become a triggering problem in the context of Bangladesh for women's reproductive health and well-being. In general, women must be aware and knowledgeable about the causes, consequences, and long-term health impacts of PCOS.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This mixed-methods study was carried out from 21 July 2024 to 21 September 2024.

Study Participants

A study conducted in Bangladesh involved a questionnaire survey of 413 women aged 15 to 45 years and older, including undiagnosed PCOS patients and women in general. The research employed focus group discussions (FGDs) for qualitative aspects and offline questionnaire methods for quantitative aspects. The study involved ten respondents each representing two distinct groups: those with PCOS and those who were symptomatic. The participants were selected from the University of Chittagong and the renowned "Strong Muscle Gym Center" fitness facility, Chattogram. The

study revealed that 72 women had PCOS, 79 were healthy, and 262 were undiagnosed.

Measures

Personal Information Form

A predesigned and pretested Personal Information Form (PIF) was used to collect sociodemographic data from the participants. The form included questions on age, height, weight, marital status, place of residence, educational background, occupation, and household income.

Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS-21)

The DASS-21 is a valid and reliable measure of psychological well-being. The DASS-21 is a condensed version of the 42-item DASS, that includes scales for depression, anxiety, and stress [14, 15]. Each of the three DASS-21 subscales has seven items. This well-known and widely used DASS-21 scale has been translated and validated in Bengali [16]. On a four-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (never) to 3 (almost always), respondents were asked about their level of mental distress over the previous four weeks. Individual scores for depression, anxiety, and stress were calculated by summing the scores of the seven corresponding items. The final scores for the three dimensions were then multiplied by two to obtain a score ranging from 0 to 42 [14, 17]. The individual scores of these three subscales were then classified into five severity categories: normal, mild, moderate, severe, and extremely severe [18].

PCOS Knowledge Scale

The PCOS Knowledge Scale is a 20-item questionnaire developed specifically for this study to assess the knowledge and awareness levels of university students regarding polycystic ovary syndrome [19]. The scale was designed to cover various aspects related to PCOS, including perceptions about the condition, signs and symptoms; treatment options; risk factors; diagnostic processes; attitudes toward doctor consultations; and views on lifestyle modifications, such as exercise and dietary habits. Additionally, the questionnaire collected demographic information, allowing for the correlation between demographic characteristics and participants' perceptions and attitudes toward PCOS.

Data Collection

This study was approved by the institutional review board (IRB) of the Bangladesh Institute of Innovative

Health Research (IRB protocol no.: BIIHR-2024-005) and was conducted following the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki [20]. All participants received comprehensive information about the nature, purpose, and procedures of the study, and informed consent was obtained from each participant before their participation. Participants were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. Privacy and confidentiality were strictly maintained, and the data were anonymized to protect the participants' identities.

Statistical Analysis

The mean, frequency, and percentage of the responses were evaluated using descriptive statistics. To evaluate the relationship between the explanatory and dependent variables, chi-square tests were used. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered to indicate a statistically significant difference. Version 27.0 of the SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) was used to perform the statistical analyses.

Results

Descriptive statistics were used in the study's quantitative analysis to determine the mean, frequency, and percentage of responses. Chi-square tests were also used to evaluate the relationships between the dependent and explanatory variables; a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered to indicate statistical significance. In addition, two focused group discussions (FGDs) narrative assessments were incorporated into the qualitative analysis to offer deeper insights into the real-life experiences of PCOS patients.

Quantitative Findings

In this research, 84.4% of the 413 women were aged 15 to under 30 years, with only 5.1% being 45 years old or older. A total of 56.6% of the participants in the study were classified as underweight, 2.7% were considered overweight and 0.7% were categorized as obese. Most of the individuals in the research resided in urban areas (84.2%), had attained higher education (66.2%), and were enrolled as students (72.2%); only a small percentage held employment (14.2%). The respondents' family income was roughly equal across the low, higher-middle, and higher-income brackets (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants (n=413)

Variables	Category	Number	Percentage
Age	15 - <30	350	84.4%
	30 - <45	42	10.2%
	45 or older	21	5.1%
BMI	Underweight	235	56.9%
	Normal	164	39.7%
	Overweight	11	2.7%
	Obese	3	0.7%

Marital status	Single	310	75.1%
	In a relationship	103	24.9%
Living place	Urban	348	84.2%
	Sub-urban	29	7%
	Rural	36	8.8%
Education	No education	14	3.4%
	Primary	8	1.9%
	Secondary	118	28.6%
	Higher study	273	66.2%
Occupation	Employed	59	14.2%
	Unemployed	56	13.4%
	Student	298	72.2%
Household income	<20,000	109	26.4%
	20,000 - 30,000	70	16.9%
	>30,000 - 50,000	127	30.8%
	>50,000	107	25.9%

Table 2: Cross Tabulation of Mental Health Conditions and PCOS Status

Mental Health Condition		PCOS status			Chi-squared value (p value)
Types	Category	Positive (n = 72)	Negative (n = 79)	Not Known (n = 262)	
Depression	Normal	15 (20.8%)	38 (48.1%)	90 (34.4%)	1082.025 (0.000)
	Mild	1 (1.4%)	4 (5.1%)	36 (13.7%)	
	Moderate	16 (22.2%)	18 (22.8%)	52 (19.8%)	
	Severe	11 (15.3%)	9 (11.4%)	37 (14.1%)	
	Extremely severe	29 (40.3%)	10 (12.7%)	47 (17.9%)	
Anxiety	Normal	15 (20.8%)	37 (46.8%)	101 (38.5%)	1053.243 (0.000)
	Mild	1 (1.4%)	3 (3.8%)	13 (5.0%)	
	Moderate	9 (12.5%)	14 (17.7%)	29 (11.1%)	
	Severe	9 (12.5%)	4 (5.1%)	37 (14.1%)	
	Extremely severe	38 (52.8%)	21 (26.6%)	82 (31.3%)	
Stress	Normal	16 (22.2%)	49 (62.0%)	131 (50.0%)	1086.824 (0.000)
	Mild	12 (16.7%)	7 (8.9%)	29 (11.1%)	
	Moderate	8 (11.1%)	7 8.9%)	45 (17.2%)	
	Severe	20 (27.8%)	11 (17.5%)	32 (12.2%)	
	Extremely severe	16 (22.2%)	5 (6.3%)	25 (9.5%)	
Total Distress	Normal	13 (18.1%)	39 (49.4%)	108 (41.2%)	1051.798 (0.000)
	Mild	4 (5.6%)	8 (10.1%)	19 (7.3%)	
	Moderate	8 (11.1%)	8 (10.1%)	28 (10.7%)	
	Severe	5 (6.9%)	2 (2.5%)	15 (5.7%)	
	Extremely Severe	42 (58.3%)	22 (27.8%)	92 (35.1%)	

Table 3: Association between Knowledge Level and Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Sub Categories	Knowledge level			Chi-squared value (p value)
		Low n = 263	Moderate n = 89	High n = 61	
Age	15 - <30	217 (62.0%)	80 (22.9%)	53 (15.1%)	1014.053 (0.000)
	30 - <45	27 (64.3%)	7 (16.7%)	8 (19.0%)	
	45 or above	19 (90.5%)	2 (9.5%)	0 (0.0%)	
Education	No education	11 (78.6%)	2 (14.3%)	1 (7.1%)	1016.124 (0.000)
	Primary	7 (87.5%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (12.5%)	
	Secondary	79 (66.9%)	18 (15.3%)	21 (17.8%)	
	Higher study	166 (60.8%)	69 (25.3%)	38 (13.9%)	
Occupation	Employed	27 (45.8%)	21 (35.6%)	11 (18.6%)	1027.419

	Unemployed	43 (76.8%)	6 (10.7%)	7 (12.5%)	(0.000)
	Student	193 (64.8%)	62 (20.8%)	43 (14.4%)	
Living place	Urban	212 (60.9%)	81 (23.3%)	55 (15.5%)	1014.214
	Sub-urban	21 (72.4%)	4 (13.8%)	4 (13.8%)	(0.000)
	Rural	30 (83.3%)	4 (11.1%)	2 (5.6%)	
Did the PCOS test	Yes	59 (39.1%)	48 (31.8%)	44 (29.1%)	1156.425
	No	204 (77.9%)	41 (15.6%)	17 (6.5%)	(0.000)
PCOS status	Positive	21 (29.2%)	20 (27.8%)	31 (43.1%)	1207.431
	Negative	38 (48.1%)	28 (35.4%)	13 (16.5%)	(0.000)
	Not Known	204 (77.9%)	41 (15.6%)	17 (6.5%)	

Table 2 reveals that women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) often experience extremely severe depression, 40.3% of whom exhibit this condition. Similarly, women without PCOS and those unaware of their condition had a greater percentage of individuals with normal depression; (48.1% and 34.4% respectively). A chi-square test revealed a significant relationship between depression and PCOS status. Anxiety levels were also found to be significantly correlated with PCOS status, with 52.8% of individuals experiencing very intense anxiety. Interestingly, stress levels were found to be significantly correlated with PCOS status, with 27.8% and 22.2% of participants experiencing severe stress. The overall distress level was found to be significantly greater in women with PCOS, with 58.3% experiencing severe distress (Table 2).

Table 3 shows that knowledge levels about PCOS vary across age groups, with 62.0% of 15 to under 30 respondents having limited knowledge and 15.1% having advanced knowledge. Education levels also showed a significant correlation with knowledge levels. Working individuals had varying degrees of understanding, with 45.8% having minimal knowledge and 35.6% having average knowledge. Unemployed individuals had lower knowledge levels, while students had 64.8%. Occupation also has a significant relationship with knowledge levels, with rural residents having the highest proportion at 83.3%. Urban residents had moderate to high levels of awareness, while rural residents had lower levels. The screening test results showed that 31.85% of the individuals had moderate knowledge and 29.1% had higher-level knowledge. Those who did not undergo testing had limited knowledge, while only 6.5% had a thorough understanding of the topic. The knowledge level was also correlated with willingness to undergo the screening test for PCOS. Those diagnosed with PCOS had a high level of knowledge, while those without PCOS had a moderate level of knowledge. The association between PCOS and knowledge about PCOS was statistically significant (Table 3).

Figure 1: PCOS Status among Bangladeshi Women

In our research, 262 women, comprising 63.4% of the sample, were not diagnosed with PCOS, indicating that they were unaware of their PCOS status, whereas only 151 (36.5%) were diagnosed with PCOS. Therefore, it is clear that the prevalence of screening or diagnostic tests is very low in Bangladesh. The majority of females in this nation have not been tested. In this study, 17.4% of the women had a positive PCOS status while 19.1% had a negative status (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Knowledge Level Regarding PCOS among Bangladeshi Women

In this research, most of the 413 women involved had varying levels of knowledge about PCOS: 63.8% had low knowledge, 21.5% had moderate knowledge, and 14.7% had high knowledge. Only, a small number of women possessed a higher level of understanding of PCOS, which could impact their choice to undergo a screening test for this condition (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Total Distress Mean Score with Respect to PCOS Status

Figure 4: Depression Mean Score According to PCOS Status

Figure 5: Anxiety Mean Score According to PCOS Status

Figure 6: Stress Mean Score According to PCOS Status

The study used the DASS-21 to assess mental health issues among women with PCOS. The average distress score for women with PCOS was 32.43, while those without PCOS had a lower score of 18.63. Women who are not diagnosed or unaware of their condition experience moderate distress (Figure 3). Women with PCOS, without PCOS, or with an unknown PCOS status had average depression scores of 11.09, 6.25, and 7.59, respectively (Figure 4). Women with PCOS experience severe depression, while those without or with an unknown status have mild or moderate depression. Women with PCOS experience high levels of anxiety, while those with unknown or negative PCOS status report moderate anxiety levels (Figure 5). The women with PCOS had a mean stress score of 11.40, while those without PCOS had a mean stress of 6.78 and those with an unknown PCOS had a mean score of 7.96 (Figure 6).

Qualitative Findings

In the qualitative segment of this study, narratives from ten individuals with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and those exhibiting symptoms without a formal diagnosis were analyzed. Two separate focused group discussions (FGDs) were conducted to explore symptoms, treatments, challenges, psychological disorders, and coping mechanisms. The first group consisted of university students from the University of Chittagong, primarily females in their 20s and 25s with substantial awareness of PCOS. Among them, four were undiagnosed despite displaying nearly all symptoms, and three had confirmed PCOS. The second group included gym members from the Strong Muscle Gym Center, Chittagong, who included both married and unmarried individuals aged between 20 to 35 years. The majority of PCOS patients in both groups first sought medical advice for irregular periods at a young age and subsequently received similar treatment protocols. Initial diagnosis involved hormone testing and ultrasonography, followed by treatment with medications for weight loss and contraceptive pills for

three months. Patients noted that no specific medication could completely cure PCOS. Doctors advised reducing dairy, packaged foods, and junk food intake. Many patients experience insulin resistance and metabolic disorders, leading to weight gain from minimal dietary indulgence. Refined sugar, particularly in sugary foods, was noted to exacerbate weight gain. Patients reported that maintaining a balanced lifestyle and regular exercise were essential for managing their condition.

Interestingly, undiagnosed individuals did not typically struggle with weight issues, with only one reporting weight concerns. Among the second group, two married respondents faced infertility issues related to PCOS, and were seeking medical help post marriage due to difficulties in conceiving. One severe case required in-vitro fertilization (IVF) for conception. Additionally, severe hair loss, alopecia, acne, and hirsutism were common, and necessitated medication for hair growth.

Respondents highlighted significant psychological impacts, with many experiencing severe depression and anxiety. Both diagnosed and undiagnosed individuals reported reactive depression and extreme mood swings, often feeling irritable and emotionally sensitive. Poor self-esteem and feelings of unattractiveness were prevalent, especially among those with hirsutism. Undiagnosed individuals exhibited higher levels of anxiety and depression, primarily due to financial barriers preventing diagnosis and treatment. Some undiagnosed individuals were warned by doctors of potential future ovarian cysts, contributing to their distress.

Discussion

Following the analysis, the study determined a substantial correlation between the respondents' characteristics and their degree of PCOS knowledge. There was also an association between respondent mental health and PCOS status.

The majority of the responders were undiagnosed but symptomatic PCOS patients, a sizable portion were PCOS diagnosed with PCOS, and the remainder were healthy. Similar findings were reported in the Haq et al. (2017) study, in which the majority of participants had indications and symptoms of PCOS but did not have a diagnosis [11]. Siddique et al. (2024) reported that the majority of students exhibited PCOS symptoms but were not identified [21].

This study revealed that the mean stress level was greater in PCOS-positive patients than in Manchanda and Bhatt, (2024), whose mean depression, anxiety, and stress levels were highest [22]. The majority of respondents had very little understanding of PCOS. This finding indicates that Bangladeshi women are not sufficiently informed about PCOS. According to Abu-Taha et al. (2020) and Rao et al. (2020), participants'

understanding of PCOS is lacking. Most participants assessed their level of PCOS knowledge as "Know some" or less [1,24].

Based on the correlation between the respondents' characteristics as an independent variable and their degree of awareness of PCOS, this study determined that those aged 15–30 years had the highest level of information about the condition, while those aged 45+ years had the lowest level of knowledge. Notably, that there is a severe dearth of awareness regarding PCOS among women with secondary and higher education. According to another study by Haq et al. (2017), the majority of the respondents were not aware of PCOS when they were educated, but after receiving education, almost every one of them was aware of the condition [11]. According to Abu Taha et al.'s (2020) research, participants' awareness of PCOS was strongly correlated with their marital status and educational attainment [1]. According to Abu Taha et al. (2020), awareness of PCOS was correlated with education and knowledge level, but this study found no association between the presence of PCOS and marital status. In this study, compared to other professional women, students possessed the highest degree of knowledge. According to Udaipur, India, there are also more students who experience anxiety due to PCOS [23].

This investigation discovered a strong relationship between the psychological states of PCOS patients, undiagnosed PCOS patients with symptoms, and healthy responders. A higher risk of psychological load is linked to the presence of PCOS. According to a 2017 study by Sulaiman et al., individuals with PCOS felt distressed and suffered from severe anxiety and panic attacks [24]. As of He et al. (2020), compared to those without PCOS, our study indicates that patients with PCOS experience extreme to severe levels of stress, anxiety, desperation, and general discomfort [25]. Depression, anxiety, low self-esteem, and mood swings are more prevalent among PCOS patients in Bangladesh, according to another study [12]. A study on the mental health of Bangladeshi women with PCOS was carried out by Hasan et al. in 2022 [26]. According to the previous studies, PCOS patients have extremely high rates of depressive illness, generalized anxiety disorder, and loneliness [26]. Similar findings to our investigation were found in another study conducted by Siddique et al. (2024), in which the participants suffered from severe stress, extremely high levels of anxiety, and considerable depression [21]. Although the majority of students may be well informed about PCOS, many are unsure about whether to take action. Additionally, research shows that most women never visit a gynecologist unless they experience serious or fatal symptoms or illnesses [23]. Despite the fact that this is a widespread condition, women frequently put off receiving a verified diagnosis and treatment

because of ignorance [9]. Patients become dissatisfied when they are diagnosed with PCOS later than they should because of challenges in diagnosing the condition during adolescence and disagreements over diagnostic criteria [27].

In contrast to the majority of studies conducted in Bangladesh and around the world, which exclusively use quantitative methods, this study used both qualitative and quantitative methods to examine not only the frequency, percentage, or significant association but also the lifetime experiences of PCOS patients and patients with PCOS symptoms.

This study aimed to identify PCOS patients and symptomatic patients among women of reproductive age in Bangladesh. However, this approach was not as successful as anticipated because the majority of respondents were of the same age group. Only conducted two FGDs were conducted, and additional patients who underwent diagnostic testing and followed the entire treatment regimen were needed to determine the true prevalence of PCOS in Bangladesh. However, qualitative research is needed to gain additional insights into the understanding and experiences of PCOS. Despite extensive research on the prevalence, awareness, symptoms, and distribution of PCOS worldwide, studies of this disease in South Asian nations such as Bangladesh are lacking. This study aimed to determine the level of knowledge and awareness among Bangladeshi women about this long-term and widely spread disease, which is beneficial for reproductive women, Bangladesh's women, and the public healthcare sector.

Conclusion

PCOS-positive women experienced adverse effects on their mental health. PCOS patients experienced a greater level of extreme distress than did individuals in the negative and undiagnosed groups. In addition, the majority of women possess a limited understanding of PCOS, which is linked to screening behaviors. This study discovered significant correlations between level of knowledge and age, education, occupation, location of residence, and PCOS status. A larger number of women in Bangladesh are undiagnosed despite showing symptoms. To determine the true frequency of PCOS in Bangladesh, it is necessary to carry out thorough screening tests on women throughout the entire country.

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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